

Title: Comparison of social quality criteria in building sustainability certification systems

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Abstract:

The growing societal demand for sustainable development has incited the building industry to develop a business of sustainability certification schemes. Prevailing sustainability certification systems are point-based systems where a proposed building design or buildings in operation can become certified if they score a sufficient number of points by demonstrating fulfilment of certain criteria. The criteria are often related to environmental-, economic-, and social aspects of sustainability with criteria regarding environmental-, and social sustainability being the most prominent.

A comparison of prevailing certification schemes using “the three pillars of sustainability” (environmental, economic, and social) as backbone organisation of criteria indicate that the schemes have different weighing of criteria within these pillars. However, the similarity of criteria for social qualities excluding weighing and benchmarks was not analysed. Such an analysis is needed to understand whether differences between schemes are due to the number of criteria for social qualities included, due to the subjective weighing of criteria or due to the inclusion of different social qualities. In this paper, we therefore present the outcome of an analysis that deconstructed the criteria organisation of prevailing building certification LEED, BREEAM (International), DGNB (Danish edition), and WELL with the aim to identify criteria related to social qualities but only criteria that 1) is related to the experience of people occupying the building, and 2) can be influenced by building design decisions. The methods used to assess the qualities are also collected for comparison; however, benchmark values and point scales are left out as they are often calibrated to national or regional legal requirements. The decomposition enabled a comparison of the inclusion of criteria related to social qualities rather than how the different schemes weigh criteria.

The comparison revealed that the four certification systems are quite similar both in terms of what social qualities they include and how they are assessed. The difference between schemes is thus to a great extent the subjective point systems and weighing. Future research could expand this study to include all criteria in the certification schemes to obtain a full and objective overview between differences and similarities.

Keywords: Building certification systems, Sustainability certification, Social sustainability, Sustainability